

THE ASSESSMENT OF INFLUENCE OF EXERCISES ACCORDING TO PILATES' METHOD IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC STATES OF SPINAL PAIN

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Introduction

Pilates therapy is one of the kinesiotherapy method, which has well-documented effectiveness in improving patients with chronic spinal pain. Pilates method comprises of various sets of preventive-curative exercises which task is to maintain or facilitate the return to fitness.

Aim of the research

The aim of the study was to evaluate the influence of exercises by the Pilates method on the improvement of the spine functioning and to reduce or eliminate pain of the patients with chronic spinal pain. The authors wanted to present to the reader the distinguishing features of therapy according to Pilates among other kinesiotherapeutic methods.

Materials and methods

The study was conducted on 30 patients. The study included 22 women and 8 men with a diagnosis of chronic spinal pain syndrome. Tests were carried out in the Jędrzej Sniadecki Regional Hospital in Białystok. The research was approved by the Bioethics Committee of Collegium Medicum in Bydgoszcz Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń. In order to reduce pain, all the patients have been treated with Pilates therapy. The patients exercised for 30 minutes every day for 10 days. All the patients filled a research questionnaire and a survey questionnaire before and after the therapy.

Results

Statistical tests showed the reduction or elimination of spinal pain suffering. A positive correlation between the time of pain reduction and the difficulty level of practiced exercises was notified. In examined patients their standing and sitting body position was improved. Moreover, the movement in lumbar part of spine was increased. Physical fitness of the examined was improved.

Conclusions

1. After completing the full session of exercises, spinal pain in standing position appears later, it is less nagging or it does not appear.
2. In 60% patients spinal pain disappearance or decrease was observed.
3. Pilates' exercises affected the increase of spine mobility in its lumbar-sacral part.
4. The value of time after which pain disappeared rises with the increase of exercise difficulty level. The easier the exercise is, the shorter time is needed to reduce pain.
5. After completing the full session of exercises, the patients' physical fitness was increased.
6. Pilates' exercises positively influence the sleep, namely they make falling asleep easy and they deepen the sleep.
7. Pilates' exercises positively influence the mood and concentration of the people researched and they improve their coordination.

Introduction

States of spinal pain are one of the most frequent causes for patients to report to GPs, rheumatologists, neurologists or orthopaedists. It is thought that about 65 – 80% of population at least once will suffer from pain in the lumbar-sacral part of the spine. In 85% of cases, the cause of chronic states of spinal pain cannot be diagnosed accurately. In Poland, sciatica constitutes 2% of all diagnoses and is one of the most common reason for incapacity to work. Chronic back pain syndrome is the most expensive medical diagnosis because treatment costs, costs associated with disability and the costs associated with lawsuits are very high. If an employee is on sick leave for more than 6 months because of a backache, the chance to return to work comes to 50%. It is estimated that in industrial districts in Britain, 1 - 5 of 100 young and middle-aged people suffer from lumbar disc herniation during a year. It is believed that in developed societies back pain will affect nearly 50% of industrial workers, mainly those in the age of maximum productivity (35 - 55 years). Frequent low back pain results among others from the adoption of an upright body posture in the process of evolution, which a spine has not been duly prepared for. More women suffer from this kind of pain (70 for 1000) than men (57 for 1000). The situation occurs more often among Caucasians (68 for 1000) than among Black (38 for 1000). The frequency of pain occurrence increases with age – in the population of adults it is 20% and it increases over 65 year of age to 50%. (Domżał 2006, Dziak 2004, Jarmużek 2004, Świerkot 2006, 2001).

World data shows that in 50% of cases, acute spinal pain stops in the period of few days to 2 weeks. In 25% the pain stops in 4 weeks and in 15% it lasts up to 3 months. Only in 10% of cases it lasts longer and it becomes chronic (Jarmużek 2004).

One of the major risk factors for spine pain syndrome is obesity. In epidemiological studies,

both positive (more often) and negative correlation was found. Obesity is a factor which affects primarily the chronicity of back pain. It is often associated with a sedentary lifestyle, low occupational status and state of mental exhaustion, as well as increased tension within the structures of the spine. A sedentary lifestyle affects the low energy consumption which contributes to the accumulation of body fat, and then leads to overweight and obesity. Such disturbances occur particularly easily in women during menopause, when hormonal and metabolism imbalance occurs (Morton 2008).

Back pains are more common with people who have problems at work (who associated it with strong expectations and were dissatisfied). Changing the scope of work and improvement of its conditions have a direct influence on improving the prognosis associated with chronic spinal pain.

One factor that may affect the chronic back pain is the weather. It was shown that the intensity of pain increases at lower temperatures and lower atmospheric pressure.

The following genetic and environmental factors also influence low back pain: mental exhaustion, bad health condition in one's own assessment, low physical activity, low education, degree of spine mobility. A factor which influences the chronic back pain is the progress of civilization, which offers us many convenient facilities (not necessarily positive) in everyday life and work. White-collar worker spends many hours in a static position (desk, machine, computer), which leads to congestion of the spine (Dziak 2004, Domżał 2006).

An intense adaptation of a young organism to a sitting position begins from an early age. Even in nurseries and kindergartens, nursery classes in seated positions are preferred, which favors the formation of faulty posture.

During the school education, children also spend a considerable number of hours in a sitting position. Whatever the age and height of the student are, a school provides chairs and tables in one size, which interferes with a correct body posture and eventually leads to low back pain (Morton 2008).

During pregnancy and postpartum period, there are favorable conditions for the occurrence or worsening of the pathology of the lower spine. Under the influence of hormonal changes, tissues flexibility (ligaments, joint capsules, etc.) changes, facilitating the movement of structures into each other. A posture along with a progress of pregnancy causes lordosis exacerbating and pelvic tilting forward, which result in pain even in the lack of disc herniation (<http://www.informed.com.pl>).

Factors contributing to the occurrence of back pain:

1. Obesity
2. High growth, in women > 170 cm in men > 180cm
3. Inefficiency of abdominal and back muscles
4. Pregnancy – sciatica occurs in 56% of pregnancies.
5. Injuries to the organs of motion
6. A sedentary lifestyle, long-term driving.
7. Doing certain sports.
8. Heavy physical work.
9. Exposure to vibration.
10. Working in an assembly line system, often repeated bending or rotation movements.
11. Personality disorders (hypochondria, hysteria).
12. Depression.
13. Progressive prolongation of life and the natural process of aging tissues connected with it.
14. Lack of moving and unwieldy or unevenly loaded muscular system.
15. Stimulants abuse (alcohol, cigarettes, drugs).
16. Posture defects.
17. Inequality of the lower limbs (Kiwierski 1997, 2005).

Treatment of chronic back pain

The effectiveness of therapeutic treatment of chronic back pain is directly dependent on accurate diagnosis - the exact cause of the pain should be taken into account. Physiotherapeutic and pharmacological treatment is essential, as well as introducing preventive measures. The medical treatment must also take periods of illness into account (Dziak, 2006, Domżał 2004, Shippide S. 2009, Stodolny J., Chmielewski, Z. 2002). The purpose of the whole process of treatment is to free the patient from distressing symptoms disrupting daily life.

Preservative treatment of chronic back pain

Preservative treatment includes pharmacological and physiotherapeutic methods as well as doing exercises which strengthen muscular corset and improve the steadiness of lumbar part by increasing of abdominal press and restoring the muscle balance which prevents from disease recurrence.

Physiotherapy

Physiotherapeutic treatment of spinal pain syndromes several methods are applied: electrotherapy, laser biostimulation, magnetic therapy, cryotherapy, thermotherapy, ultrasound, phonophoresis, paraffine, hydrotherapy, phototherapy. The following methods also play an important role in treatment: kinesitherapy treatment, massage, therapy with the use of lifts, manual therapy, McKenzie method of treatment.

Among the physiotherapeutic treatment methods which have beneficial effects on spinal pain syndromes the following should be mentioned: transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation TENS, iontophoresis, diadynamic, interference currents, anode plating and electrical stimulation. One of the most effective methods of electrotherapy is Transcutaneous Electrical Nerve Stimulation (TENS).

These treatments are primarily analgesic, anti-inflammatory, relaxing, improving blood circulation (Kurpas D., A. Steciwko 2008).

Proceedings in the acute stage

In the acute stage, bed regime typically lasting a few days is obligatory (2 - 3 days). Each patient is given an individually selected analgic position in which the muscles are relaxed and a patient does not feel pain. The position is usually lying on the back or lying on the side with legs bent in hip-joint and in the knee at 90°. This position reduces lumbar lordosis, pelvic anteversion and relaxation of tense ischio - venous muscles.

In this period, pharmacological treatment that relieves pain is applied.

After reducing the intensity of pain, physiotherapeutic treatment and individual exercises are used: respiratory and loosening exercises, isometric trunk muscles exercises. Exercises are performed with a firm stability of the pelvis and suppressed lumbar lordosis. In case of strong back pain, lumbar distraction applies. This method reduces lumbar lordosis, unloads locomotive segment, and thus reduces pain. During this period, laces and corsets stabilizing the spine may be helpful. However, a patient should be advised to shape their own muscle by regular exercises. Patient education should be implemented in the treatment of a patient in the acute stage.

During this period, thermal treatments such as sollux, paraffine, short wave diathermy, and mud treatment are contraindicated (P Liński, 2006).

Fig. 1. Algorithm of the back pain treatment during the acute period.

Proceedings during the chronic stage.

Back pain which lasts more than six weeks is considered chronic. During exacerbations of pain, the rehabilitation procedure is similar to that of the acute stage.

In the chronic period of the disease, it is necessary to choose an appropriate set of gymnastics exercises. It is necessary to maintain a strong muscular corset by systematic use of isometric exercises, shaping exercises, general fitness, consolidating correct posture patterns and movement habits. Exercises with resistance should be introduced to the programme after the disappearance of pain.

Moreover, during chronic period pharmacological therapy, physiotherapeutic treatments, massage, and psychotherapy are used.

Relief of pain does not provide a cure. Patient should be aware that the damaged segment of the motor is a steady, weak point, which requires the care of maintaining conditions which prevent from recurrence of symptoms. We educate patients about risk factors, which are mostly lifting heavy things, especially on the outstretched legs and avoiding overloading axial spine.

If all preservative treatment measures prove to be ineffective, then that it is an indication for a surgery. A clinical study during the classification must clearly indicate the prolapsed nucleus

pulposus and an occurrence of complex neurological symptoms (Kwolek A, 2004).

Fig. 2 Algorithm of the back pain treatment during the chronic period.

Prevention of spinal pain syndrome

Prevention of back pain is primarily based on preventing from overloading of the spine. This issue is complex and covers all periods of human life and all areas of people's activity. Exercises which ensure a proper performance of the motion organs are very important, however we should remember to adjust them to individual abilities of patients.

The patient education should include the causes of pain, provide a treatment plan, discuss a correct posture and daily exercises. It is essential to make the patient realize about the risk of symptoms relapse and the necessity of performing appropriate exercises and avoidance of abnormal

loads of the back through a patient's whole life. The elimination of predisposing factors is important as well. In the education of a patient, the essence of the necessity to change lifestyles should be explained as well as the importance of body weight reduction. Patients should be aware that we cannot avoid certain changes, but we can prevent from their escalation (Dziak 2004, Domżał 2006).

In people who have an episode of back pains it is advised to shape a strong muscular corset training (every day for 15 - 20 minutes of exercising) and achieve a proper body weight. It is important to learn and practice appropriate patterns of performing basic movements. The patient should learn how to practically apply the correct movements mentioned above during daily routines and professional activities. Items and equipment, which force overloading movements or positions, should be eliminated from a patient's surrounding and exchanged into those items or equipment, which save the back as much as possible. A patient should learn the correct forms and methods of relaxation, recreation and physical activity.

In case of the symptoms of spine overload disease occurrence, the type and nature of work, daily activities and equipment should be adjusted to the type of disorders. The patient should be isolated from the situation causing chronic excessive stress, which is one of the reasons of pain. Immune system strengthening exercises against stressful factors should be applied.

Prevention during walking - relatively energetic walking is recommended, clearly leaving the rear leg behind. When walking, you should maintain a clear hyperextension of the hip. It is recommended to walk every day on uneven ground. Sports shoes should be worn most often. Footwear should be comfortable and have a flexible, shock-absorbing sole. Walking in clogs is not recommended. Wearing high-heeled shoes should be moderate, as they increase the inclination of the pelvis forward and they load lumbosacral spine. (Stodolny J. 2002, Niedzielski W. 2005, Liński P, 2006).

Prevention during standing - during long-standing, stretching of all the muscles in legs every five minutes should be applied, keeping the tension in each group for 3 - 5 seconds. It is recommended to support the torso during working hours. While standing, one ought to lean the back on a wall, the buttocks on a high stool, their forehead against a wall for example, as well as to support with the shoulder or with one hand during performing activities in a slight anteversion. Shoes for a standing job should be comfortable with a wide cushioning heel and should stabilize the ankle joint well. Posture at work should be changed every 20-25 minutes.

Prevention of seating - the correct furniture for sitting should not be too soft nor too low. A chair for working and learning must be able to be regulated in various ways, so that it can be adapted to the individual characteristics of one's body built. Feet should be firmly on the ground and knees must be bent at right angle. Thighs lie horizontally on the seat. In the lumbar part lordosis should be forced while sitting. In case of little ability to sustain lumbar lordosis, different types of supportive means or a material wedge which raise the seat behind are worth using additionally on the back of the chair. While sitting, hands should lie on the armrests. Buttocks should be tucked under the back of the chair as deep as possible, so that they can push lumbar spine forward. During work, people should try as often as possible to prop their elbows on a countertop or armrests, thereby offsetting the burden of arms (Świerkot 2006).

Prevention during sleep - the mattress in the bed should be of equal hardness. Sleeping both on a totally hard ground or on beds which collapse archwise under the weight of the body is not advised. A neck and a head should be supported in a neutral position, without excessive bending forward or hyperextending backward. People should sleep on a plastic cushion that can be formed to sustain both cervical lordosis and occipital bone. During the sleep, the body regulates by itself positions of setting the body and the frequency of their changes, avoiding congestion and causing back pain. Position during sleep should ensure the maintenance of normal body functions and particularly the physiological shape of the spine, including a skull and a pelvis (Stodolny J. 2002).

Prevention during lifting and moving loads - while lifting the load from the ground one should stand perfectly opposite and as close as possible to the subject which is going to be lifted. Then, feet should be put on both sides of the object, so that the object lifted is between them (one

foot extended slightly forward than the other). Another element of the safe loads lifting is to crouch with knees splayed. Then one grabs the load with their hands and presses it to the trunk. Bent hip and knee joints are straightened and the load is raised by the strength of lower limbs muscles. One should remember that pushing heavy objects forces the spine less than pulling. Even small loads transmitted with the outstretched hands can cause congestion of the spine (Śliwiński Z. 1999).

Kinesitherapy method, which has well-documented efficacy in improving patients with chronic spinal pain, is Pilates therapy.

Pilates method is a system of physical exercises invented in the early twentieth century by the German Joseph Pilates, whose aim was to stretch all the muscles of the body and to make them more flexible. The Pilates system is a combination of yoga, ballet and isometric exercises. According to the assumptions of Pilates, this method helps to strengthen muscles without excessive building them up, relieve the spine, improve posture, make the body more flexible, lower stress levels and improve the overall health of the people exercising. The uniqueness of the Pilates method, among other things, is that it brings not only physical benefits but also psychological ones. It improves the appearance of the whole body, and also a positively influences our mood. It reduces pain in the spine and joints and teaches proper breathing habits.

Pilates Method comprises of various sets of preventive-curative exercises, whose task is to maintain or facilitate the return to fitness. Pilates method is characterized by maintaining the balance between the mind (philosophy of the East) and physical aspects of the human body, such as strength, endurance and proper mobility (thinking of the West).

In order to achieve the expected therapeutic result by performing Pilates exercises, people should remember about eight main principles which are characteristics for this method.

Principle I – Concentration

It assumes a maximum focus on the performance of the exercises in a proper manner.

The key to success in the Pilates training system is the involvement of the whole body in the physical activity. This kind of concentration encourages the develop consciousness of the whole body, namely a sensitivity to the influence of individual muscle movements on the body as a whole. Focusing allows to take control over the muscles and move in the desired way and not being forced by harmful habits.

For this purpose, the visualization of the movement is used, which is imagining the movement before and during its conduct.

Principle II – Control

During exercises, the mind controls their performance so that they are not harmful. Muscle fatigue is avoided through precise performance of a small number of repetitions of exercises including the difficulty grading system and the introduction of breathing and stretching exercises into the course of training sessions. The Pilates method, sensory-motor control is designed to restore normal neuromuscular coordination, based on a deep awareness of the performance of motor actions.

Fig. 3. Exercise of restoring proper neuromuscular control - movement of pelvic anteversion in the closed biokinetic chain for the lower limbs.

Fig. 4. Exercise of restoring proper neuromuscular control - movement of the pelvis retroversion in the closed biokinetic chain for the lower limbs.

Fig. 5. Exercise of restoring proper neuromuscular control - concentric work for quadratus lumborum muscle in a closed biokinetic chain for the lower limbs.

Principle III - Strong body center – centering

It is a neutral, stable posture achieved by upright body posture and strong abdominal and back muscles.

The movement for each exercise is preceded by muscle tension and obtaining so called 'cylinder of stability' around the spine. It consists, in particular, of deep musculofascial structures: in the front abdominal muscles – transverse abdominal muscle and internal obliques, at the back - multifidus muscle, at the top – diaphragm, and at the bottom muscles of the pelvic floor. The Pilates technique, activating 'cylinder of stability' is performed by a transverse abdominal muscle tension ("pull the navel to the spine") and by tensing the muscles of the pelvic floor. In this method, learning of proper activating of the center of the body is implemented since the first classes. In classic Pilates exercises, muscles directly affecting the functioning of the hip joints are particularly involved into movement. This follows the assumption of obtaining a "strong center" because the function of abducent and adducent hip muscles, gluteal muscles and latissimus dorsi muscles (because of the location of their attachments to spine and pelvis) affects the stabilization of the center of the body. Well stable spine with pelvic ring is the foundation of economical movement in the upright position of the human body. This favors the elimination of transverse sliding movements in the joints of the spine and allows to make freer movements of limbs. Muscle structures located in the deep layers of the body, near its center, have their attachments directly to the spine or the pelvis and are defined as the muscles of the middle of the body. Their main activity consists of formation of a strong core stabilization, which is necessary to perform the basic movement activities, such as standing, sitting, walking, bending or grasping and lifting objects.

Today's lifestyle, the development of civilization, injuries or muscle balance disorders as a result of bad muscles habits, weakens and limits the functions of "deep stabilizers of the body." In case of impaired function of muscle of the center of the body, a core stabilization function is taken over large groups of muscles located externally (trapezius muscle, the muscle of the back extensors - superficial layers). This leads to chronic tension and fatigue of these structures, which results in the occurrence of back pain.

Activating the deep trunk muscles aims to form an automatic and functional stabilization of the trunk and ergonomics, flexibility and lightness in a daily physical activity.

Fig. 6. Exercise involving the deep stabilizers of the spine

Principle IV – Breathing

Without it, life would be impossible, but it does not mean that we can breathe properly. We use only a small part of our lungs and often we do not know how to breathe deeply with the diaphragm or by broadly extending the chest.

Proper coordination of breathing with performing exercises is the first method implemented in teaching Pilates. Proper breathing helps in better blood oxygenation and thus in better work of mind and control movement. Costal – diaphragmatic breathing is used, with an emphasis on strengthened exhaust with pulling the navel to the spine at the same time. With inspiration, the rib cage expands in three dimensions, with strengthened exhaust abdominal obliques are additionally involved, which allows better ventilation of the lungs.

'Pilates' teachers talk about wide or side breathing. Wide breathing in contrast to the deep breathing, uses the work of intercostal muscles to the maximum extent. Breathing is imagined as a movement of the ribs back and forth, but the chest is also extended to the sides. To breathe broadly, we fill lungs with air until we feel slight receding of the shoulders from each other as the body expands.

Another element influencing the way of breathing is the diaphragm. Diaphragm work changes the shape and volume of the chest, which allows the inhalation and exhalation of air. Contraction of muscle fibers lowers the diaphragm and reduce the pressure in the thoracic cavity, which allows an inspiration. The movements of the diaphragm are independent of the will, but can be modified by a human being.

During Pilates exercises, breath should never be held. Breathing, like any other movement, should be seamless and continuous.

The general principle of breathing during the exercises:

- breathe in while you perform movement
- breathe out while you return to the starting position.

If during the exercise we take too little breath and before returning to the starting position we have run out of air, we inhale once again.

Principle V - Maintaining proper body position

One of the greatest benefits of the Pilates method is an ability to maintain the correct upright

and relaxed posture. A proper posture is important during the exercises and helps to achieve maximum effect with minimum effort involved. In Pilates method, a conscious trying to maintain correct body alignment during all phases of the exercise is emphasized. All the movements are performed in the neutral position, without deepening the physiological curvatures of the spine. A proper posture is a system of individual sections of the body not affected by the changes, which provides optimal balance and stability of the body, requires minimal muscular effort, provides a large static-dynamic capacity and creates the conditions for proper alignment and operation of the internal organs.

Proper posture is a condition of proper physical and mental development.

Head and neck.

Attention is paid to maintaining the head without extending it forward in motion of protraction. A head should be positioned exactly in the middle between the arms.

Arms and shoulders.

Shoulders should be positioned without elevation resulting from excessive tension - 'ear distance from the shoulder'. The ears should be on one line with the shoulders. Your arms fall loosely to the sides. Arms should be set to the same level. Viewing from the side, arms are not overly swung backward or forward.

Back and abdomen

Shoulders should be slightly pushed toward the buttocks. Standing, remember to actively extend the body along the long axis of the spine - "distance from the foot to the crown. " The natural curvatures of the spine should not be in any way exacerbated or reduced.

"Navel to spine" is the basic theme of Pilates . By pulling the navel to the spine, the tension in the center of the body is created.

Pelvis

According to the Pilates method, setting the pelvis is a key factor in the correct posture. From the side, the pelvis should not be extended either forward or backward. This causes misalignment of the lumbar spine.

Legs and feet

Gently bend your legs without blocking knee joints and symmetrically load whole feet situated from each other by the width of pelvis. Feet should be facing forward.

Fig. 7. Exercise involving the transverse and the ascending part of trapezius muscle with a closed biokinematic chain for upper limb.

How to properly stand by the method of Pilates?

To feel comfortable in an upright position and have relaxed muscles, you need to adjust to all the six points:

1. Spacing of feet on hips width.
2. Make sure both feet are facing forward.
3. Straighten your legs, so that you do not block them in your knees.
4. Hands should hang naturally on the sides and reach the hips.
5. Carry half your weight on each leg.
6. While standing, do not carry weight on heels and toes (do not swing back or forward).

Principle VI – Fluency

The pace of exercises in the Pilates method is moderate and dependent on the precision of movement performed and the individual rhythm of breathing. One must practice being focused, and all body movements, even at the starting position changes, should be implemented in a smooth manner.

In exceptional circumstances, the movement must be rapid and determined, but even then, fluency and self-control is necessary. Due to this, we will move prettier, but above all, we will avoid the risk of joints injury, arthritis, and our muscles will not lose control over the exercise performed. This improves the safety of people, even after suffering injuries.

Fig. 8. Exercise to improve neuromuscular coordination.

Principle VII – Endurance

Classes are conducted with a level of training loading, adjusted to the ability of the people exercising. In group classes, it is advised to divide them into beginners and advanced.

Classical Pilates exercises are designed in several versions, depending on the fitness level of athletes. The method aims to increase the overall endurance of the entire muscular system.

Fig. 9. Exercise to improve endurance of back muscles and gluteal muscles.

Rule VIII-Relaxation

An essential element of proper exercises performing in Pilates method is to acquire the skill of conscious relaxation of certain muscle groups. Performing the elements of exercises accurately is designed to eliminate the accumulating tension in the spine and shoulder belt.

According to the assumptions of this system, the movement combined with the concentration of the mind and breath, performed in a gentle but precise way, leads to new more ergonomic motor behaviors, and also brings psychological benefits of reducing stress levels.

12 golden rules of the Pilates method

- Always start with a warm-up.
- Do not rush! The slower you practice, the better.
- Practice in accordance with the rhythm of your breath.
- Insert the entire effort to exhale.
- When you exhale, pull the navel toward the spine.
- Control your posture.
- Concentrate on what and how you're doing.
- Expand the strength of the abdominal muscles slowly - if they highlight during the exercises, take a break.
- Start movement of the arms from the largest muscles of the back and four sides, and not from the same shoulder.
- Quality is important, and not quantity! Follow the given number of repetitive exercises.
- Pilates Exercise perform regularly, preferably daily.
- Only with endurance will you obtain pretty and shapely figure.

There are varied systems of exercises according to the method of Pilates.

In the above method, exercises are performed on a mat or using special equipment designed by the inventor of the system, Joseph Pilates. (Zembaty A. 2003, Selby A. 2003, Seattle S. 2006, Rydeard R. 2006, Meţel S, Milert A. 2007, Austin D. 2003, Blount T.,2006).

As with other forms of exercise, there are times when you should avoid exercising. Pilates Method training system is safe for everyone, however there are some precautions that should be followed.

Contraindications to the use of exercises using the Pilates method:

– Pregnant women in the first trimester should avoid exercising. Some Pilates exercises are safe at a later stage of pregnancy. However, pregnant women before exercise should always consult their doctor before starting to exercise and follow the guidance of qualified therapist of Pilates, to adjust exercises programme to the conditions of their pregnancy.

Pilates Training System is a great way to return to the good physical form after giving birth, but a safe time to begin your workout should be consulted with your doctor.

- In the case of an injury that causes pain, it is necessary to consult a therapist. It is worth to wait until symptoms subside, than to start classes immediately.
 - In case of severe pain requiring the use of analgesics, you should wait with starting classes, where it is possible to stop them. Analgesics mask the pain and during exercise you cannot be aware of any other sensations of pain associated with the performance of movements, which can lead to injury. You should not in any way force your body to do more than it is able to.
 - Do not exercise after a heavy meal – up to two hours.
 - Do not exercise after drinking alcohol or taking drugs that affect the well-being (eg, sedatives).
- Keep in mind that, apart from other contraindications, you cannot concentrate properly on exercises.
- People with cardiovascular disease.
 - People with diseases and disorders of the skeletal and muscles systems.

- In the course of any treatment, you should consult your doctor before starting Pilates exercise method.
- Make sure to tell your Pilates therapist about undergoing therapy, illnesses or injuries and also about being on a diet (Chantsoulis M. 2006, Domżał 2006, Dziak 2004, Cielak J. 2006).

Aim of the research

The aim of the study was to evaluate the influence of exercises by the Pilates method on the improvement of the spine functioning and to reduce or eliminate pain of the patients with chronic spinal pain. The authors wanted to present to the reader the distinguishing features of therapy according to Pilates among other kinesitherapeutic methods.

Material and methods

The research covered the group of 30 patients. In this study 22 women and 8 men were classified with chronic back pain. The studies involved people aged from 18 years old.

Spinal pain syndrome in patients researched took longer than 2 weeks. Patient's mental state had to allow to understand and fill in a questionnaire. The study involved patients who after reading the information about the experiment, agreed to participate in it by writing a consent.

Before the beginning of each test, the patient was informed about the purpose of the study, and the possibility to resign from the participation in the study at any stage, without giving reasons. Patients participating in the study had access to the results of observations obtained in each stage of the study. Each patient had the opportunity to ask the leader questions and receive a reply. All people participating in the survey signed a written consent to participate in the research.

The research was held in Wojewódzki Szpital Zespolony im. Jędrzeja Śniadeckiego in Białystok (Jędrzej Sniadecki Voivodship Complex Hospital). The research approval was issued by Biotic Commission of Collegium Medicum in Bydgoszcz of Mikolaj Kopernik University in Torun.

Before and directly after the research, all patients taking part in it filled in an examination questionnaire. Patients filled in the questionnaires after completing the treatment. In the research group, the exercises of Pilates method was used in order to reduce pain. The exercises took 10 days, 30 minutes every day. The examination questionnaire covered data concerning age and sex of the patient. The questionnaire included functional test assessing spine mobility, that is the test of distance from the finger tip to the floor.

The examination questionnaire assessed:

- spinal pain ailment,
- body posture.

The survey form included 23 questions concerning the influence of Pilates' method exercises on health condition of patients with states of spinal pain. The survey form was anonymous. Patients filled the form by themselves on the last day after completing the exercise session.

The survey form included questions concerning the assessment of:

1. difficulty level of the exercises,
2. physical fitness before and after exercises,
3. the influence of exercises on sleep,
4. well-being, concentration and coordination,
5. the influence of exercises on comfort during sitting and standing,
6. the influence of exercises on everyday activity.

Results

STATISTICA software was used for preparing obtained results. In statistical analysis there were descriptive statistics techniques applied, such as: arithmetic mean, correlation ratio and standard deviation. The research results are presented in tables and figures below.

After a 2-week therapy of Pilates' exercises, the following was stated: 60% of patients (18 people) noticed reduction or disappearance of spinal pain, 16,7% of patients (5 people) noticed no improvement, whereas in case of 23.3% patients (7 people) it could not be stated whether pain symptoms had been reduced or remained similarly intense and of the similar character. According to the carried research, it was noticed that in 25 patients (83.3%) pain ailments were eliminated, decreased or they did not lead to other pain.

Ailment disappearance	Number of patients	percentage	Accumulated percentage
Yes	18	60	60
No	5	16.7	76.7
Hardly to say	7	23.3	100
Sum	30	100	

Table 1. The assessment of spinal pain ailment reduction after exercises according to Pilates' method.

After carrying the research, the correlation between time of pain reduction or disappearance and the difficulty of exercise level was noticed. It is statistically relevant correlation in which time of pain reduction or disappearance correlates positively with the level of difficulty of Pilates' method exercises ($p < 0.002$ $r = 0.538$).

The above data may lead to the conclusion that the value of time after which pain symptoms disappeared increases with the level of difficulty in the following way: the more difficult exercise was in patient's judgement, the longer the time was needed to decrease pain.

p – statistical relevance r - correlation

Figure I. The correlation between the time of pain reduction or disappearance and the level of difficulty of exercises.

It was stated that average value of the finger tips – floor distance before exercises was reduced in

relation to average value of the distance after exercises. Mean and standard deviation of the test after exercises were lower in comparison to values obtained before therapy (average of 13.07 ± 16.603 to 14.77 ± 16.606).

The average of subtraction result of the distance in the test before and after exercising was 1.7 cm for the whole group of tested patients (average 1.700 ± 3.142).

Test	Average	Number of patients	Standard deviation
Test of finger tips – floor distance before exercising	14.77	30	16.606
Test of finger tips – floor distance after exercising	13.07	30	16.603

Table 2. The results of finger tips – floor distance test before and after exercising for the whole research group: arithmetic average and standard deviation.

Spine mobility increased in patients after exercising. The group of 29 patients (96.7%) positively judged the influence of exercises on spine mobility, which was supported by the data obtained from the functional test of the finger tips to floor distance that was measured before and after exercising.

After exercises, 17 patients (56.7%) stated that exercises according to Pilates' method were quite easy, 8 patients (26.7%) judged exercises as easy. Only 5 patients (16.6%) found the exercises difficult and very difficult. The research showed that the group of 25 patients (83.3%) did not find exercises according to Pilates' method difficult.

25 people (83.3%) who were asked, if the exercises were excessively exhausting, answered negatively.

Difficulty level	Number of patients	Percentage	Accumulated percentage
Easy	8	26.7	26.7
Quite easy	17	56.7	83.3
Difficult	4	13.3	96.7
Very difficult	1	3.3	100
Sum	30	100	

Table 3. The assessment of difficulty level for the exercises according to Pilates' method applied in chronic states of spinal pain.

Patients' physical fitness was assessed and it increased after exercises in comparison to fitness presented before exercising. Before starting the exercises, 1 person (3.3%) judged themselves as very weak but after 10 days there were no such opinions. 4 patients (13.3%) stated their fitness as weak before exercises and after exercises only 1 patient (3.3%) did not change his opinion. Satisfactory fitness before exercises was reported by 13 patients (43.3%), and after exercises only 5 patients (16.7%) described their fitness as satisfactory. 7 patients reported quite good fitness before the examination (23.3%), after examination there were 9 such patients (30%). Good fitness was declared by 5 patients (16.7%) before exercising and it was changed into the number of 46.7% (14 patients) after full session of exercises. 1 patient (3.3%) found his physical fitness as very good after exercises and before exercises there were no such opinion. After full session of exercises 19 patients (63.3%) stated that their physical fitness improved.

Physical fitness assessment	Number of patients	Percentage	Accumulated percentage
Very weak	1	3.3	3.3
Weak	4	13.3	16.7
Satisfactory	13	43.3	60
Quite good	7	23.3	83.3
Good	5	16.7	100
Very good	0	0	100
Sum	30	100	

Table 4. Physical fitness assessment before exercises.

Physical fitness assessment	Number of patients	Percentage	Accumulated percentage
Very weak	0	0	0
Weak	1	3.3	3.3
Satisfactory	5	16.7	20
Quite good	9	30	50
Good	14	46.7	96.7
Very good	1	3.3	100
Sum	30	100	

Table 5. Physical fitness assessment after exercises.

For the question of the survey form "Do Pilates' exercise affect sleep?", 16 patients (53.3%) confirmed the influence of exercises on sleep, 14 patients (47.7%) did not feel the influence on the character of sleep. Another question the patients had to answer was "Do Pilates' exercises make falling asleep easier, make falling asleep hamper, deepen the sleep, shallow the sleep, make it longer or shorter?" The patients answered as follows: exercises make falling asleep easier – 14 people (46.6%), deepening the sleep – 8 people (26.75%), making the sleep longer – 2 people (6.7%), making the sleep shorter and shallower – 3 people (10%).

After exercising, 14 patients (46.7%) reported that pain during sitting is milder. Additionally, 5 patients (16.7%) noticed that they could sit longer without pain ailments. In 6 patients (20%) no pain ailment during sitting was observed. Pilates' exercises affect the improvement of sitting comfort. Pain disappearance or extension of the period without symptoms of pain had a positive influence on body positioning during performing variety of everyday activities.

The assessment of mood, concentration and coordination

The study shows that 93.3% of respondents feel a positive impact of exercises on mood. 3 people, that is 6.7% had a problem with defining this state responding to this question as "It's hard to say." However, 90% of patients stated that the performed exercises made them happy. 80% of respondents said the performed exercises had beneficial effects on improving concentration.

After analyzing the survey, it turned out that 70% of respondents felt improvement of coordination, and 30% of respondents replied that the exercise does not affect the fluency of their movements. It should be noted that no patient had deterioration of coordination.

These data shows that the method of Pilates exercises have a positive impact on the well-being of patients, their concentration and coordination. Most patients found the exercises fun and satisfactory.

All patients stated that Pilates' exercises made breathing easier and breathing exercises done during session had direct positive influence on the whole organism

Carried research showed that 100% of examined patients would like to take part in Pilates' exercises sessions in the future. 100% of patients declared that Pilates' exercises should be introduced in specialistic centres of rehabilitation and that the exercises should be done at home as well.

Discussion

Chronic state of spinal pain is one of the most serious problems of the contemporary medicine. In recent years the number of patients suffering from the above illness is ominously increasing. It is stated that 65-80% of population over 50 years old has at least one episode of spinal pain (Domżał T.M. 2006, Dziak 2004, Jarmużek P. 2006, Kiwerski 2005).

In most cases of states of spinal pain it possible to eliminate or to ease the pain. There are many physiotherapeutical methods with analgetic effect. One of them are exercises according to Pilates' method. In available literature there is no assessment of Pilates' method exercises effectiveness in patients with spinal illnesses, therefore looking for analgetic influence of the above method seems to be justified (Selby A. 2003, Rydeard R, 2006).

According to Hermann, the above method affects the respiratory system, increases muscular force and endurance. Moreover, it positively influences motor coordination (Kiwski 2005). It is connected with the improvement of physical fitness as it has been proved in presented research.

According to Basford's, Hein's and Segal's observations, spine mobility increases after Pilates' exercises. In the researchers' opinion, the result of the distance lengthening test (finger tips to floor) is increased if we compare the values before and after exercises, as we also showed in this dissertation (Kiwski 1997, Kurpas D. 2008 La Touche R, 2008, Langauer – Lewowicka H. 2007).

According to Blount and Mc Kenzie, Pilates' exercises positively influence patients' physical fitness as they force correct examples of body position with simultaneous pain relieving (Jarmużek 2004). Our research confirmed the authors' observations.

A 10 day therapy of Pilates exercises used in the research improved the well-being of the patients, which positively correlates with reduction or disappearance of spine pain. One of the very important aspects in treating spine diseases is prevention by learning to acquire correct body posture during every day activities. The research presented in this article proves the efficiency of exercises by Pilates method and indicates their usefulness in treating patients with chronic spine pains.

Conclusions

1. After completing the full session of exercises, spinal pain in standing position appears later, it is less nagging or it does not appear.
2. In 60% of patients spinal pain disappearance or decrease was observed.
3. Pilates' exercises affected the increase of spine mobility in its lumbar-sacral part.
4. The value of time after which pain disappeared rises with the increase of exercise difficulty level. The easier the exercise is, the shorter time is needed to reduce pain
5. After completing the full session of exercises the patients' physical fitness was increased.
6. Pilates' exercises positively influence the sleep, namely they make falling asleep easy and they deepen the sleep.
7. Pilates' exercises positively influence the mood and concentration of the people researched and they improve their coordination.

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